
Series: PHYSICS

Khmelnik S.I.ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>

Stubborn Heaviside was right after all

Annotation

Here the Heaviside gravity equations are refined. It is proven that they are completely similar to Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism and predict the existence of gravitational waves propagating at a certain speed. Next, we consider a rigorous mathematical assessment of the speed of movement of these waves, based on the results of Samokhvalov's experiments. Based on this assessment, the gravitoelectric and gravitomagnetic permeability of vacuum are calculated.

The article appeared as a response to a recent publication [1].

Contents

Heaviside's gravity equations
Application
References

Heaviside's gravity equations

Maxwell's equations for the gravitational field in the form proposed by Heaviside are known. Here we refer to the work [1], in which Heaviside's theory of gravity is analyzed and an explanation is given for the fact that it was not accepted by the scientific community. Subsequently, it was shown [2] that in a weak gravitational field at low speeds, from the basic equations of general relativity it is possible to derive gravitational analogues of the electromagnetic field equations, which have the same form (3).

"The idea of the similarity of the laws of gravity to the laws of electromagnetism was discussed by J. C. Maxwell, Brillouin, Bridgman, O. Heaviside, G. Bondi (1962), E. Braginsky and others. R. Forward (1961) derived gravity relations similar to Maxwell's based on A. Einstein's general relativity. J. Karstua (1969) obtained the same system of gyrofield equations, based on the idea of isomorphism of the basic laws of electromagnetism and gravity" [3].

Next we will consider Heaviside's gravity equations in the form of Maxwell's equations.

Table 1.

ε - the dielectric constant	ε_g - gravitodielectric constant
μ - magnetic permeability	μ_g - gravitomagnetic permeability
E - electric field strength	E_g - gravitoelectric field strength
H - magnetic field strength	H_g - gravitomagnetic field strength
B - magnetic induction	B_g - gravitomagnetic induction
J - electric current density	J_g - mass current density
ρ - electric charge density	ρ_g - mass density
c —speed of a traveling electromagnetic wave (speed of light)	c_g - speed of traveling gravitomagnetic wave

To formulate these equations, consider the table. 1. In the indicated notation and in the SI system, Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism take the known form:

$$\operatorname{div}E = \rho/\varepsilon, \tag{1}$$

$$\operatorname{div}H = 0, \tag{2}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}E = -\mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}, \tag{3}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}H = J + \varepsilon \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \tag{4}$$

or, instead of equations (3, 4),

$$\operatorname{div}E = \rho/\varepsilon, \tag{5}$$

$$\operatorname{div}B = 0, \tag{6}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}E = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}, \tag{7}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}B = \mu J + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t}, \tag{8}$$

where

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}}. \tag{9}$$

Heaviside also has almost the same appearance as (5-8):

$$\operatorname{div}E_g = -\rho_g/\varepsilon_g, \tag{10}$$

$$\operatorname{div}B_g = 0, \tag{11}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}E_g = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B_g}{\partial t}, \tag{12}$$

$$\operatorname{rot}B_g = -\mu_g J_g + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial E_g}{\partial t}. \tag{13}$$

There are two differences that the authors of [1] point out:

- 1) Negative signs appeared in equations (10) and (13). Hence, according to the authors of [1], the fatal conclusion for Heaviside's theory follows that in this theory the energy flow is negative. But in Application this conclusion is refuted.
- 2) In equations (12) and (13) the speed c is indicated, not c_g . It means that

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_g \epsilon_g}} \tag{14}$$

Therefore, it is further proposed to use the following form of the Heaviside equations:

$$\text{div}E_g = -\rho_g/\epsilon_g, \tag{15}$$

$$\text{div}B_g = 0, \tag{16}$$

$$\text{rot}E_g = -\frac{1}{c_g} \frac{\partial B_g}{\partial t}, \tag{17}$$

$$\text{rot}B_g = -\mu_g J_g + \frac{1}{c_g^2} \frac{\partial E_g}{\partial t}, \tag{18}$$

where

$$c_g = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_g \epsilon_g}} \tag{19}$$

This system of equations is equivalent to the following:

$$\text{div}E_g = -\rho_g/\epsilon_g, \tag{20}$$

$$\text{div}H_g = 0, \tag{21}$$

$$\text{rot}E_g = -\mu_g \frac{\partial H_g}{\partial t}, \tag{22}$$

$$\text{rot}H_g = -J_g + \epsilon_g \frac{\partial E_g}{\partial t} \tag{23}$$

Such equations are completely analogous to the equations of electromagnetism and predict the existence of gravitational waves.

Traveling gravitational waves move at speed c_g .

Stubborn Heaviside was right!

Table 2.

	SI system	GHS system
G	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{sec}^{-2}$	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{sec}^{-2}$
ϵ_g	$1.5 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg} \cdot \text{sec}^2$	$1.5 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g} \cdot \text{sec}^2$
μ_g	$7 \cdot 10^{-53} \text{ m} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$	$7 \cdot 10^{-54} \text{ cm} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$
ξ	$10^{12} \div 10^{13}$	$10^{12} \div 10^{13}$
c	$3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m} \cdot \text{sec}$	$3 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm} \cdot \text{sec}$

In [2] it is shown that based equations of general relativity and assuming that the gravitational field is weak, equation (20) can be written as

$$\operatorname{div} E_g = -G\rho_g. \quad (24)$$

where G is the gravitational constant. Therefore (see Table 2),

$$\varepsilon_g = 1/G \quad (25)$$

So, in the weak gravitational field of the Earth, one can use Maxwell-like Heaviside equations to describe gravitational interactions. This means that there are gravitational waves that have a gravitoelectric component with strength E_g and a gravitomagnetic component with induction B_g . A mass m moving in a magnetic field with a speed v is acted upon by the gravitomagnetic Lorentz force (analogue of the known Lorentz force) of the form (in the GHS system)

$$F = \zeta \frac{m}{c} [v \times B_g], \quad (26)$$

where ζ is a coefficient equal to 1 in Heaviside and equal to 2 in general relativity. In accordance with the above, we must write this formula in the form:

$$F = \frac{m}{c_g} [v \times B_g]. \quad (27)$$

In [4], unexpected and surprising experiments by Samokhvalov are considered and analyzed, which can be explained (according to the author of this article) by the interaction of uneven mass currents. Uneven mass currents J_g create variable gravitoelectric strength E_g and gravitomagnetic induction B_g . When this induction interacts with masses v moving at speed v , a gravitomagnetic Lorentz force arises. It is important to note that the effects manifest themselves in the form of Lorentz forces and are so significant that to explain them, equation (26) must be supplemented with some empirical coefficient ξ . Further in [4] it is shown that with this addition, the experimental results are in good agreement with equation (26), which takes the form:

$$F = \xi \frac{m}{c} [v \times B_g]. \quad (28)$$

Comparing (27, 28), we find:

$$c_g = \xi c. \quad (29)$$

The value of the coefficient ξ from these experiments is determined for reduced pressure. Its value at atmospheric pressure can be estimated very approximately. This coefficient can be called the gravitational permeability of the medium. From Samokhvalov's experiments it follows that

$$\xi \approx 10^{12} \div 10^{13}. \quad (30)$$

From (19, 29, 27) we find:

$$\mu_g = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_g c_g^2} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_g \xi^2 c^2} = \frac{G}{\xi^2 c^2} \approx \frac{10^{-25} G}{c^2}. \quad (31)$$

Thus, we have determined the value of all constants in the Heaviside equations - see table. 2.

Application

In [1], Heaviside's theory of gravity is considered and it is shown that the equations of electromagnetism and the equations of gravity coincide up to notation - see equations (5-8) and (10-13), respectively. The only difference is the appearance of a negative sign in equations (10) and (13). It follows that the energy flow in the gravitational equations is negative, which, of course, is unacceptable for physical theory.

The authors confirm this conclusion by discussing an experiment with a moving charged rod. In this case, the direction of the charge current inside the rod coincides with the direction of the energy flow, which moves in the same direction, but outside the rod. This phenomenon is equivalent to the fact that the electric current inside the rod is accompanied by a flow of energy outside the rod. Feynman analyzes this paradox in his famous lectures [5]: *our "crazy" theory says that electrons receive their energy, which they waste to create heat from the outside, from the flow of external field energy into the wire. Intuition tells us that the electron replenishes its energy due to the "pressure" that pushes it along the wire, so that the energy seems to flow down (or up) the wire. But the theory states that in fact the electron is acted upon by an electric field created by very distant charges, and the electrons lose their energy, which is spent on heat from these fields. The energy from distant charges somehow spreads over a large area of space and then flows into the wire."*

The reason for this paradox is that solving the equations in the form of a wave equation (mathematically correct) does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy. As a result, physically unfounded consequences appear. A stream of energy flying from the side of a wire is one of them.

In [6], other solutions to Maxwell's equations were found in which the law of conservation of energy is observed. In this case, in particular, the energy flow appears inside the wire - see Chapter 5.

The same solutions exist for the Heaviside equations under consideration. In this case, the energy flow becomes positive regardless of the sign in equations (10) and (13). Thus, Heaviside's equations of gravity do not violate any physical laws.

The main question posed by the authors of the paper under discussion is whether Heaviside's theory predicts gravitational waves. From the above, the answer follows in the affirmative.

References

1. F. Herrmann, M. Pohlig. Heaviside's Gravitoelectromagnetism: What is it good for and what not?
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369977648>
2. Gravitoelectromagnetism,
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gravitoelectromagnetism>
3. E.O. Schultz On the issue of global vortex radiation. ANDJournal of Emerging Directions of Science,number 12(4), pp. 184-185, 2016, <http://www.unconv-science.org/n12>
4. S.I. Khmelnik. Gravitomagnetism: Nature's Phenomenas, Experiments, Mathematical Models. 2020. Third Edition, pp. 1–283. "MiC" - Mathematics in Computer Corp. Israel, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3802903>
5. R.P. Feynman, R.B. Leighton, M. Sands. The Feynman Lectures on Physics, volume 2, 1964.
6. S.I. Khmelnik. Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations. In Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations. 2021.Edition19, pp. 1–378. "MiC" - Mathematics in Computer Corp., Israel, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796226>